

CALIBRATION OF THE GFRP-CONCRETE COHESIVE MATERIAL LAW USING PULL-OUT TESTS

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ABSTRACT

Glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars are currently used to reinforce concrete members when durability is the main concern. Indeed, when exposed to aggressive conditions, traditional steel bars rapidly corrode affecting the performance of the reinforced concrete member. GFRP bars are available with various surface treatments, each providing a peculiar GFRP-concrete bond behavior. The GFRP-concrete bond behavior is usually investigated using the pull-out test. In this paper, results of GFRP-concrete pull-out tests are used to calibrate the GFRP-concrete interfacial cohesive material law (CML) that describes the relationship between the bar-concrete interface shear stress and the corresponding slip.

KEYWORDS

Pull-out Tests, GFRP Bars, Bond, Interfacial cohesive material law (CML)

INTRODUCTION

Due to their strength-to-weight ratio, mechanical properties, and durability (Fib, 2001), fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have become popular in the civil engineering field. FRP composites are utilized as externally bonded for strengthening applications and as internal reinforcement in reinforced concrete structures. In the latter case, FRP bars are preferred to traditional steel bars (Carvelli et al., 2010; Mufti & Neale, 2008; Pendhari et al., 2008) in regions with de-icing salts or chloride-rich environments. Among the various FRP bars available, glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars are highly favored due to their low cost. Despite the availability of guidelines for concrete members made with FRP bars (ACI 440, 2015; CNR, 2007; CSA, 2009), certain open issues remain, such as creep and fatigue behavior. The presence of different fiber, and external surface condition in the market contributes to the unpredictability of FRP bar-concrete bond behavior, necessitating studies to investigate their unique bond behavior (Zhao et al., 2022). In the case of FRP-reinforced concrete members, design considerations revolve around deformability and crack width under service load (Mazaheripour et al., 2013). Consequently, studying the stress between the embedded FRP reinforcement and the concrete is of paramount importance as it significantly affects crack opening and evolution (Bernardi et al., 2014; C. Mias, L. Torres, M. Guadagnini, A. Turon, 2015; El-Nemr et al., 2016). The simplicity of the concentric pull-out test make it the preferred method for investigating the bond behavior between FRP bars and concrete. The current practice (ASTM, 2020) limits the investigation to a bonded length (ℓ) of $5d_b$, where d_b is the nominal diameter of the FRP bar. Researchers have found that concrete strength (Ehsani et al., 1997; Lee et al., 2008) and external surface treatment of FRP bars (Mazaheripour et al., 2013) can influence the FRP-concrete behavior, further highlighting the limitations of the ASTM D7913 (ASTM, 2020) model. In this study, pull-out test results of GFRP bars embedded in concrete cylinders, obtained from the authors' previous study (Zhao et al., 2022), were used. Different bonded lengths, namely $5d_b$, $10d_b$, $20d_b$, $30d_b$, and $40d_b$ (where $d_b=12$ mm), were considered.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Material properties

The experimental study considered a GFRP bar that had a sand coating and featured a helically wrapped carbon yarn, as shown in Figure 1a. According to the manufacturer datasheet (Sireg Geotech

S r. l., 2017), the bar had a diameter of 12.7 mm, the Young's modulus was 46 GPa, the tensile strength was 950 MPa. In this paper, the nominal diameter of the bar (d_b) was considered equal to 12 mm. Tensile tests conducted on the GFRP bars yielded an average tensile strength of 1025 MPa based on three tests. All the pull-out specimens and cylinders (for material characterization) were cast from the same batch of concrete. The mix proportion for the concrete was as follows: water, cement, fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate in a ratio of 1:2.5:6.7:7.7. The maximum aggregate size was 12.8 mm. The slump value, determined according to (ASTM C09, 2020b), was measured at 89 mm. At 28 days, the average concrete compressive strength (f'_c), tested in accordance with (ASTM C09, 2020a), was 34 MPa. The average splitting tensile strength (f'_t), tested following (ASTM C09, 2017), was measured at 2.94 MPa. Further details regarding the material properties can be found in (Zhao et al., 2022).

Specimen preparation

Pull-out specimens consisted of a GFRP bar embedded in a concrete cylinder. Different bonded lengths (ℓ) were considered and were chosen as multiples of the nominal bar diameter d_b , i.e., $5d_b$, $10d_b$, $20d_b$, $30d_b$, and $40d_b$. Cylindrical tubes and plywood bases were used to fabricate the molds for the pull-out specimens. A PVC pipe of 140 mm was used to create a bond breaker between GFRP bar and concrete near the top end of the concrete cylinder. A protruded portion of the bar was present at the bottom of the cylinder (free end) for all the specimens except $\ell=30d_b$ specimens, since this bonded length was obtained from cutting longer specimens. After casting, specimens were left to cure for 24 hours. After that, specimens were demolded and moist cured under wet burlap sealed with plastic. The curing process was continued for 28 days. Additional details of the specimen preparation can be found in (Zhao et al., 2022).

Test setup

In accordance with the recommendations of ASTM D7913, the test set-up involved restraining the concrete cylinder containing an embedded GFRP bar between two steel plates. These plates, named top and bottom plates, were connected using four steel rods. To measure the slip at the loaded end of the bar (referred to as g), three linear variable displacement transformers (LVDTs) were installed. Two additional LVDTs were positioned at the bottom of the cylinder to measure the slip at the free end (δ). To ensure secure gripping of the bar by the jaws of the servo-hydraulic testing machine, a threaded hollow cylinder was used at the bar end (Figure 1b). For a detailed description of the test set-up, please refer to (Zhao et al., 2022). Specimens equipped with the bottom LVDTs were controlled by monotonically increasing the average displacement of the top three LVDTs at a rate of 0.88 mm/min. On the other hand, specimens without the bottom LVDTs were subjected to stroke (t) control, with a rate of 1.3 mm/min. The rate was increased during the test (Zhao et al., 2022).

Results and discussion

The cylindrical pull-out specimens were designated using the notation X-Z, where X represents a letter ranging from A to E, identifying the bonded length ($A=5d_b$, $B=10d_b$, $C=20d_b$, $D=30d_b$, and $E=40d_b$). Z is a unique number assigned to differentiate specimens with the same ℓ . The relationships between the applied load (P) and the loaded end slip (g) for all the conducted pull-out tests are reported in (Zhao et al., 2022). g was derived from the average of the top three LVDT readings. The elastic elongation of the GFRP bar, corresponding to the portion of the bar between the point where the top LVDTs were mounted and the beginning of the bonded area, was subtracted from the average readings of the top three LVDTs. The load responses (Figure 2a) exhibit an initial linear branch, followed by a limited non-linear branch, before reaching the peak load P^* . Beyond the peak load, the descending phase of the response is characterized by load oscillations with increasing slip (g) as a result of the surface characteristics of the GFRP bar. The plots of the applied load P against the free end slip δ , i.e., the average readings of the bottom LVDTs for specimens equipped with these LVDTs, are also reported in (Zhao et al., 2022) and are shown in Figure 2b. The plots indicate that the free end slip δ begins to deviate from zero at different percentages of the peak load depending on the bonded length.

Figure 1: GFRP bar used in specimens and the pull-out test setup (Zhao et al., 2022)

INTERFACIAL COHESIVE MATERIAL LAW (CML)

The experimental results described above were used to calibrate an interfacial CML which associates the interfacial slip s (bar-concrete relative displacement) with the corresponding interfacial shear stress τ at any location of the interface.

Selection of the specimens used in the calibration process

Table 1 summarizes the results of the pull-out tests used in this paper to determine the CML that describes the interaction between the GFRP bar investigated and concrete. Specimens with $\ell = 360$ mm were not considered, as their responses are not comparable with those of the remaining specimens, due to the absence of the protruding part of the bar. The P - g and P - δ responses of selected specimens were used to determine the average P - g and P - δ responses corresponding to four values of ℓ , i.e., 60 mm, 120 mm, 240 mm, and 480 mm. Specimens were selected to compute the average curves if the difference g - δ was lower than $P\ell/(E_b A_b)$ for any point of the P - g and P - δ responses (Zhao et al., 2022), where E_b and A_b are the longitudinal elastic modulus and cross-sectional area of the bar, respectively. Specimens not equipped with LVDTs at the free end (the measurement of the free end slip δ was not available for those specimens) were selected, which was necessary since the number of specimens equipped with the bottom LVDTs was limited. Further research shall be carried out to investigate the relationship between g - δ and $P\ell/(E_b A_b)$ and its effect on the procedure presented below.

Table 1: Specimens used to obtain the average P - g and P - δ responses

Spec.	ℓ [mm]	P - g avail.	P - δ avail.	Sel.	Used for P - g_{all}	Used for P - g_{fe} and P - δ	Spec.	ℓ [mm]	P - g avail.	P - δ avail.	Sel.	Used for P - g_{all}	Used for P - g_{fe} and P - δ
A-01	60	x		✓	x		B-07	120	x	x			
A-02	60	x		✓	x		B-08	120	x		✓	x	
A-03	60	x		✓	x		C-01	240	x		✓	x	
A-04	60	x	x				C-02	240	x		✓	x	
A-05	60	x		✓	x		C-03	240	x		✓	x	
A-06	60	x	x	✓	x	x	C-04	240	x	x	✓	x	x
A-07	60	x		✓	x		C-05	240	x		✓	x	
A-08	60	x	x				C-07	240	x	x	✓	x	x
B-01	120	x		✓	x		C-08	240	x		✓	x	
B-02	120	x		✓	x		E-01	480	x		✓	x	
B-03	120	x		✓	x		E-02	480	x	x	✓	x	x
B-04	120	x		✓	x		E-03	480	x		✓	x	
B-05	120	x	x	✓	x	x	E-04	480	x	x	✓	x	x
B-06	120	x	x				E-05	480	x		✓	x	

Specimen B-06 was not selected, since its load responses were characterized by pull-out forces considerably higher than the pull-out forces of the remaining specimens having the same bonded length $\ell = 120$ mm. The specimens selected are identified with a \checkmark mark in Table 1. For each ℓ , two average P - g responses and one average P - δ response were derived from the experimental data. One average P - g response, referred to as P - g_{all} response (Figure 2a), was obtained based on the P - g responses of all selected specimens.

Figure 2: Experimental P - g and P - δ responses considered in the calibration process

The other average P - g response, referred to as P - g_{fe} response (Figure 2b), was obtained based on the P - g responses of all selected specimens for which the free end slip δ was measured (the subscript fe indicates that the free end slip was available for those specimens). The average P - δ response was obtained based on the P - δ responses of all selected specimens for which the free end slip δ was measured. The specimens used to construct the P - g_{all} , P - g_{fe} , and P - δ responses are identified with a \times mark in Table 1. The P - g_{all} response, for the selected specimens with a given bonded length, was determined by averaging the pull-out force P associated with any loaded end slip g . For the selected specimens with bottom LVDTs and a given ℓ , the P - g_{fe} and the P - δ responses were determined by averaging the pull-out force P and the free end slip δ associated with any loaded end slip g . A-06 and B-05 were the only specimens with $\ell = 60$ mm and $\ell = 120$ mm, respectively, that exhibited g - δ lower than $P\ell/(E_b A_b)$. Thus, the P - g_{fe} and P - δ responses for $\ell = 60$ mm and $\ell = 120$ mm coincide with the P - g and P - δ responses of those two specimens.

Governing equations of the bond phenomenon (Mode-II)

The shear stress transfer (fracture mechanics Mode-II) at the bar-concrete interface in a pull-out test is governed by the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dy} s(y) = \varepsilon_b(y) - \varepsilon_c(y) \\ \frac{d}{dy} N_b(y) = \pi d_b \tau(y) \\ \frac{d}{dy} N_c(y) = -\pi d_b \tau(y) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where y is a reference axis coincident with the axis of the bar, d_b is the diameter of the bar (in this Section the actual diameter, i.e., 12.7 mm, rather than the nominal is used), $s(y)$ is the interfacial slip at the coordinate y (i.e., relative displacement between the surface of the bar and the surface of

concrete at the coordinate y), $\varepsilon_b(y)$ and $\varepsilon_c(y)$ are the strain of the surface of the bar and concrete at the coordinate y , respectively, $N_b(y)$ and $N_c(y)$ are the axial forces in the bar and concrete at the coordinate y , respectively, and $\tau(y)$ is the bar-concrete interfacial shear stress at the coordinate y . First equation in Eq. 1 is derived from the definition of the slip. Second and third equations in Eq. 1 enforce the equilibrium conditions of a small element of bar and concrete of length dy , respectively. Once the boundary conditions are assigned, the differential system in Eq. 1 allows to determine the slip profile $s(y)$ and the strain profiles $\varepsilon_b(y)$ and $\varepsilon_c(y)$ (or the axial force profiles $N_b(y)$ and $N_c(y)$). The solution of the system requires that the constitutive relations between the axial forces $N_b(y)$ and $N_c(y)$ and the strains $\varepsilon_b(y)$ and $\varepsilon_c(y)$ at the bar-concrete interface are known, and the relation between the shear stress $\tau(y)$ and the functions $s(y)$, $\varepsilon_b(y)$ and $\varepsilon_c(y)$ (or $N_b(y)$ and $N_c(y)$) are defined. Under the assumptions: i) the strain is constant in the cross-sections of bar and concrete; ii) the concrete and the bar are linear elastic; iii) the interfacial shear stress τ at the coordinate y depends only on the interfacial slip at the same location, i.e., $\tau(y) = \tau(s(y))$, the system in Eq. 1 becomes

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dy}s(y) = \varepsilon_b(y) - \varepsilon_c(y) \\ \frac{d}{dy}\varepsilon_b(y) = \frac{\pi d_b}{E_b A_b} \tau(s(y)) \\ \frac{d}{dy}\varepsilon_c(y) = -\frac{\pi d_b}{E_c A_c} \tau(s(y)) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where E_b and A_b and E_c and A_c are the elastic modulus and cross-sectional area of the bar and concrete, respectively. Because of assumptions i) and ii), the axial forces in the bar and concrete are written as a function of the corresponding strains ($N_b(y) = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(y)$ and $N_c(y) = E_c A_c \varepsilon_c(y)$). The system in Eq. 2 can be reduced to a second order differential equation by substituting the second and third equations into the first equation. If the concrete strain is negligible compared to the strain in the bar (i.e., $E_b A_b / E_c A_c \rightarrow 0$), this equation is:

$$\frac{d^2}{dy^2}s(y) = \frac{\pi d_b}{E_b A_b} \tau(s(y)) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

and the strain of the bar surface is equal to the derivative of the slip $s(y)$. When the geometrical and mechanical parameters are assigned and the dependence of the interfacial shear stress τ on the slip are defined, Eq. 2 or Eq. 3 can be used to determine the functions $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$, which associate the loaded end slip g and the free end slip δ of a pull-out specimen with bonded length ℓ to the corresponding pull-out force. The $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ functions will be referred to as the analytical load responses or analytical $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ responses. Assuming the origin of the y -axis at the free end of the bar, in the case of Eq. 2, the boundary conditions

$$s(0) = \delta \quad \varepsilon_b(0) = 0 \quad \varepsilon_c(0) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

can be enforced for increasing values of the free end slip δ . This allows a slip profile $s(y)$ and a bar strain profile $\varepsilon_b(y)$ to be associated with any value of δ . A pull-out force $P_\ell = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(\ell)$ and a global slip $g = s(\ell)$ are then associated with any value of δ . In the case of Eq. 3, the boundary conditions

$$s(0) = \delta \quad \varepsilon_b(0) = \varepsilon_b(0) = \left. \frac{ds}{dy} \right|_0 = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

can be enforced for increasing values of the free end slip δ . This allows a slip profile $s(y)$ and a bar strain profile $\varepsilon_b(y) = ds/dy$ to be associated with any value of δ . A pull-out force $P_\ell = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(\ell)$ and a global slip $g = s(\ell)$ are then associated with any value of δ . If the relation between the shear stress and the slip is such that the free end slip δ is zero up to a finite value \bar{P}_ℓ of the pull-out force, the initial branch of the $P_\ell(g)$ function (up to \bar{P}_ℓ) can be determined by enforcing the boundary conditions in Eq. 4 or Eq. 5 with $\delta = 0$ at different distances ξ from the loaded end (i.e., the origin of the y -axis is placed at the distance ξ from the loaded end). A loaded end slip $g = s(\xi)$ and a force $P_\ell = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(\xi)$ are then associated with any value of ξ in the range $[0, \ell]$ (Focacci & Carloni, 2015).

Calibration process based on the P - g and P - δ responses corresponding to each bonded length

If the CML is expressed through a certain set of parameters, the procedure described above can be used to determine the analytical $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ responses, which will in turn be associated with the same set of parameters for any ℓ . The parameters can be determined by minimizing the distance between the functions $P_\ell(g)$ and/or $P_\ell(\delta)$ and experimental P - g and/or P - δ responses. In this paper, this procedure has been applied to the average P - g and/or P - δ responses (Figure 2) described above. The least square criterion has been adopted to evaluate the distance between the experimental and the analytical responses. The distance between the analytical and the experimental responses has been evaluated considering a P - g response (P - g_{all} or P - g_{fe}), a P - δ response, and a P - g_{fe} and a P - δ response simultaneously. A piecewise multilinear CML function was considered in this work. In particular, an array of slips $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k, s_{k+1}, \dots, s_n]$ was defined for each ℓ , where $s_1 = 0$ and s_n is the maximum slip in the P - g response used to calibrate the CML (if a P - δ response was used, s_n was the maximum slip of the P - g response associated with the P - δ response used). Slips s_j ($j = 1, \dots, n$) were arranged in ascending order in \mathbf{s} . The shear stresses corresponding to the slips in \mathbf{s} were collected in the array $\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_k, \tau_{k+1}, \dots, \tau_n]$ and were the parameters of the CML which were determined by the calibration process. The shear stress τ corresponding to a generic slip s between s_j and s_{j+1} is determined by linear interpolation between the points with coordinates (s_j, τ_j) and (s_{j+1}, τ_{j+1}) in the τ - s plane. The distance $\Delta s = s_{j+1} - s_j$ ($j = 1, \dots, n-1$) between two consecutive slips in \mathbf{s} was constant but different for $j \leq k-1$ and $j \geq k$. In particular, Δs was smaller for $s \leq s_k$ than for $s > s_k$ to obtain a more refined evaluation of the first branch of the CML. For each ℓ , four different piecewise multilinear CMLs were obtained by adjusting the values of the shear stresses in the array $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ to minimize the distance between: i) the $P_\ell(g)$ and the experimental P - g_{all} response; ii) the $P_\ell(g)$ and the experimental P - g_{fe} response; iii) the $P_\ell(\delta)$ and the experimental P - δ response; and iv) the $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ and the experimental P - g_{fe} and P - δ responses, simultaneously. These CMLs were denoted as $\text{CML}_{Pg,all}^\ell$, $\text{CML}_{Pg,fe}^\ell$, $\text{CML}_{P\delta}^\ell$, and $\text{CML}_{Pg\delta}^\ell$, respectively, where ℓ is the bonded length of the specimens used in the calibration process expressed in millimeters. In particular, the $\text{CML}_{Pg,all}^\ell$ and $\text{CML}_{Pg,fe}^\ell$ associated with each bond length were determined by minimizing the function:

$$f_1(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(P_j^{\text{exp}} - P_\ell(g_j) \right)^2 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where g_j and P_j^{exp} were the loaded end slip and corresponding pull-out force of the P - g_{all} or P - g_{fe} responses considered, and N was the number of points in the mentioned responses. The $\text{CML}_{P\delta}^\ell$, and $\text{CML}_{Pg\delta}^\ell$ associated with each bond length were determined by minimizing the functions:

$$f_2(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(P_j^{\text{exp}} - P_\ell(\delta_j) \right)^2 \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$f_3(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{j=1}^N \left[\left(P_j^{\text{exp}} - P_\ell(g_j) \right)^2 + \left(P_j^{\text{exp}} - P_\ell(\delta_j) \right)^2 \right] \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

respectively. In Eq. 7 and in Eq. 8, δ_j was the free end slip of the average P - δ response considered, which corresponds to the loaded end slip g_j in the companion P - g_{fe} response. The analytical $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ responses introduced in Eq. 6, Eq. 7 and Eq. 8 were constructed with the procedure described above by increasing the free end slip δ in the boundary condition in Eq. 5 until δ was

greater than δ_N (i.e., the maximum free end slip of the experimental response considered) and a loaded end slip $g = s(\ell)$ greater than $s_n = g_N$ was obtained. Figure 3a shows the CMLs obtained. Figure 3b shows the average CMLs, which were obtained by averaging the CMLs corresponding to different bonded lengths and derived from the same minimizing criterion and experimental responses.

Figure 3: CMLs obtained through the calibration procedure

The average CMLs were named $CML_{P_{g,all}}$, $CML_{P_{g,fe}}$, $CML_{P_{\delta}}$ and $CML_{P_{g\delta}}$. Superscript ℓ was dropped because they corresponded to the averages for all bonded lengths. Given the bonded length, minimizing one of the functions in Eq. 6, with the $P_{g,all}$ or the $P_{g,fe}$ responses, Eq. 7, or Eq. 8 (which implies using different average experimental responses) resulted in consistent CMLs. On the other hand, the CMLs obtained using the same minimizing criterion and with average experimental responses of specimens with different ℓ were inconsistent (Zhao et al., 2022). Figure 4a reports the average experimental responses $P_{g,fe}$ and P_{δ} for all bonded lengths. The analytical $P_{\ell}(g)$ and $P_{\ell}(\delta)$ responses obtained by introducing in Eq. 3 the $CML_{P_{g,fe}}^{\ell}$ with $\ell = 60$ mm, $\ell = 120$ mm, $\ell = 240$ mm, and $\ell = 480$ mm (Figure 4a-d) are plotted for comparison. The $P_{\ell}(g)$ and $P_{\ell}(\delta)$ responses shown in Figure 4 were labeled in such a way that it was possible to identify which CML was used to obtain them. A superscript X , i.e., $P_{\ell}^X(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^X(\delta)$, was added and referred to the bonded length ℓ used to calibrate the $CML_{P_{g,fe}}^{\ell}$. The subscript ℓ in $P_{\ell}^X(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^X(\delta)$ was made explicit to refer to the bonded length used to solve Eq. 3. For example, in Figure 4c the $P_{480}^{240}(g)$ curve was obtained by solving Eq. 3 in the range $[0, \ell = 480 \text{ mm}]$ and using the CML calibrated with $\ell = 240$ mm obtained by minimizing the distance between the analytical $P_{\ell}(g)$ and the experimental $P_{g,fe}$ responses (see Eq. 6), i.e., $CML_{P_{g,fe}}^{240}$. Each plot in Figure 4 includes a sub-plot where the four $CML_{P_{g,fe}}^{\ell}$ are shown and the one used in Eq. 3 to construct the analytical $P_{\ell}^X(g)$ in the plot is identified with a black line. Each $CML_{P_{g,fe}}^{\ell}$ allows to obtain analytical $P_{\ell}^X(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^X(\delta)$ responses similar to the experimental $P_{g,fe}$ and P_{δ} responses for the same bonded length ℓ used to calibrate the CML itself, i.e., the analytical and experimental responses are similar when $X = \ell$. On the other hand, the pull-out force of the $P_{\ell}^X(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^X(\delta)$ functions tend to overestimate (or underestimate) the pull-out force of the corresponding experimental responses for $X > \ell$ (or $X < \ell$). A similar observation applies if $CML_{P_{g,all}}^{\ell}$, $CML_{P_{\delta}}^{\ell}$, and $CML_{P_{g\delta}}^{\ell}$ are used to derive the analytical responses.

Figure 5 reports the analytical $P_{\ell}(g)$ and $P_{\ell}(\delta)$ responses (labeled $P_{\ell}^{av}(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^{av}(\delta)$) obtained by introducing the $CML_{P_{g,all}}$, $CML_{P_{g,fe}}$, $CML_{P_{\delta}}$, and $CML_{P_{g\delta}}$ (Figure 3b) in Eq. 3. $P_{\ell}^{av}(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^{av}(\delta)$ are compared in the same figure with the experimental $P_{g,all}$, $P_{g,fe}$ and P_{δ} responses. It can be observed that $P_{\ell}^{av}(g)$ and $P_{\ell}^{av}(\delta)$ tend to overestimate the experimental pull-out forces for long bonded lengths and underestimate the experimental pull-out forces for short bonded lengths.

Calibration process based on the $P-g$ and $P-\delta$ responses corresponding to all bonded lengths

A different calibration approach was used to predict simultaneously all the experimental responses. The CMLs obtained by minimizing the distance between the analytical and the experimental

responses corresponding to all the bonded lengths were called *global* CMLs. Similarly, to the previous case, i) the P - g_{all} response; ii) the P - g_{fe} response; iii) the P - δ response, and iv) the P - g_{fe} and P - δ responses simultaneously were used. The functions minimized during the calibration process were:

$$\bar{f}_1(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_\ell} \left[\sqrt{f_{1,k}(\boldsymbol{\tau})} / P_{\max,k} \right]^2 \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$\bar{f}_2(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_\ell} \left[\sqrt{f_{2,k}(\boldsymbol{\tau})} / P_{\max,k} \right]^2 \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$\bar{f}_3(\boldsymbol{\tau}) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_\ell} \left[\left(\sqrt{f_{1,k}(\boldsymbol{\tau})} + \sqrt{f_{2,k}(\boldsymbol{\tau})} \right) / P_{\max,k} \right]^2 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

where N_ℓ was the number of bonded length considered, $P_{\max,k}$ is the maximum experimental pull-out load corresponding to the k^{th} bonded length, and $f_{1,k}(\boldsymbol{\tau})$ and $f_{2,k}(\boldsymbol{\tau})$ are evaluated with Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 with the experimental and analytical responses corresponding to the k^{th} bonded length ($k = 1, \dots, 4$).

Figure 4: $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ obtained with different CMLs

The CMLs obtained by minimizing function in Eq. 9 with the P - g_{all} and P - g_{fe} responses were named $\overline{CML}_{Pg,all}$ and $\overline{CML}_{Pg,fe}$, respectively, whereas the CMLs obtained by minimizing functions in Eq. 10, and in Eq. 11 were named, $\overline{CML}_{P\delta}$, and $\overline{CML}_{Pg\delta}$, respectively. In this case, it was assumed $s_k=6$ mm and the number of elements in \mathbf{s} was chosen so that $\Delta s=0.38$ mm for $j \leq k-1$, and $\Delta s=0.98$ mm for the $\overline{CML}_{Pg,all}$ and $\Delta s=0.83$ mm for the remaining global CMLs when $j \geq k-1$. Figure 6 shows the comparison between the average CMLs ($\overline{CML}_{Pg,all}$, $\overline{CML}_{Pg,fe}$, $\overline{CML}_{P\delta}$, and $\overline{CML}_{Pg\delta}$) and the global CMLs ($CML_{Pg,all}$, $CML_{Pg,fe}$, $CML_{P\delta}$, and $CML_{Pg\delta}$). It can be observed that very similar results are obtained by averaging the CMLs calibrated based on the load responses corresponding to different bonded lengths and by using a calibration method that simultaneously considers the load responses corresponding to different bonded lengths. In particular, the initial branches (roughly up to 5 mm) of the CMLs in Figure 6 are almost overlapped. Figure 7 compares the $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ functions, obtained by introducing the average and the global CMLs in Eq. 3, with the P - g_{all} , P - g_{fe} , and P - δ responses.

Figure 5: $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ obtained with different average CMLs

$P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ obtained by introducing the global CMLs in Eq. 3 are labeled $\overline{P}_\ell(g)$ and $\overline{P}_\ell(\delta)$, respectively. It can be observed that the $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ functions obtained with the average and global CMLs underestimate the experimental pull-out forces of specimens with short bonded lengths and overestimate the experimental pull-out forces of specimens with long bonded lengths.

Discussion

From the calibration approaches described above, it can be argued that a unique CML that allows to capture the experimental responses of pull-out specimens with different bonded lengths cannot be found

for the bar considered in this paper. Two phenomena, which have been neglected in the previous analysis, can be assumed to influence the experimental load response and could justify the difference between the analytical load responses associated with the average and global CMLs and the experimental load responses.

Figure 6: Comparison of the average and global CMLs

Figure 7: $P_\ell(g)$ and $P_\ell(\delta)$ obtained with the average and global CMLs

These phenomena are: i) the dependency of the interfacial shear stress by the axial strain of the bar due to the Poisson's ratio effect, and ii) the effect of the protruded part of the bar which produces a resistance to the slippage of the bar when it is pulled inside the concrete block. Referring to the first phenomenon, it can be observed that the specimens with longer bonded lengths (for which the experimental pull-out responses is overestimated by the analytical responses associated with the average and global CMLs) are subjected to higher pull-out forces than specimens with shorter bonded length (for which the experimental pull-out response is underestimated). Thus, it is possible that, for a given slip s , the shear stress decreases as the axial stress (or the axial strain) in the bar increases. This effect can be considered by introducing in Eq. 1 the shear stress τ as a function of the slip s and axial strain in the bar ε_b , i.e., $\tau = \tau(s, \varepsilon_b)$ or in Eq. 3 a shear stress τ depending also on the derivative of the slip (in addition to the slip). The dependence of the shear stress τ on the bar strain ε_b can be calibrated together with its dependence on the slip s , based on the load responses corresponding to different bonded lengths and Eq. 9, Eq. 10, or Eq. 11. Referring to the second phenomenon, it can be observed that the resistance to slippage provided by the protruded part of bar is independent on the bonded length and therefore it is relatively higher for the shorter bonded lengths. This is consistent with the overestimation (underestimation) of the experimental results by the analytical load responses provided by the average and global CMLs for the longer (shorter) bonded lengths. The effect of the protruded part of bar can be considered by introducing a resisting force P_e at the free end depending on the free end slip δ , i.e., defining a $P_e(\delta)$ function which associates any free end slip δ with the corresponding resisting force P_e . This force modifies the boundary conditions in Eq. 4 or Eq. 5 when constructing the load responses. Function $P_e(\delta)$ can be calibrated together with the CML, based on the load responses corresponding to different bonded lengths and Eq. 9, Eq. 10, or Eq. 11. Alternatively, the calibration process can be divided in two phases: the first phase consisting in the calibration of the CML based on the load responses of specimens without protruding part of bar, and the second phase consisting in the calibration of the $P_e(\delta)$ function only. These effects will be considered in a future step of this research.

CONCLUSIONS

Two alternative procedures were applied for the calibration of the bar-concrete interfacial CML based on the results of pull-out tests of specimens with various bonded lengths. The first procedure averaged different CMLs, each determined based the results of specimens with a certain bonded length.

The second procedure simultaneously considers the results of specimens with different bonded lengths. For both procedures, different experimental load responses were considered, namely the relation between the loaded end slip and the pull-out force, the relation between the free end slip and the pull-out force, and simultaneously both these relations. From the calibration analysis the following conclusions can be outlined for the bar considered in this work.

1. The CMLs obtained based on different experimental load responses are very similar to each-other.
2. Very similar CMLs are obtained with the two procedures.
3. Specimens with different bonded lengths were considered when calibrating the interfacial CML, since a CML calibrated based on results of pull-out specimens with a certain bonded length overestimated (underestimated) the results of specimens with longer (shorter) bonded length.
4. The dependency of the interfacial shear stress on the longitudinal strain of the bar associated with the Poisson ratio, and the effect of the protruding part of the bar at the free end should be taken into account. Further analysis is needed to assess these phenomena.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- ACI 440. (2015). *Guide for the design and construction of structural concrete reinforced with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) bars* (ACI 440.1R-15).
- ASTM. (2020). *ASTM D7913/D7913M-14. Standard Test Method for Bond Strength of Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite Bars to Concrete by Pullout Testing*.
https://www.astm.org/d7913_d7913m-14.html
- ASTM C09. (2017). *Standard Test Method for Splitting Tensile Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens*. ASTM International. https://doi.org/10.1520/C0496_C0496M-17
- ASTM C09. (2020a). *Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens*. ASTM International. https://doi.org/10.1520/C0039_C0039M-20
- ASTM C09. (2020b). *Standard Test Method for Slump of Hydraulic-Cement Concrete*. ASTM International. https://doi.org/10.1520/C0143_C0143M-20
- Bernardi, P., Cerioni, R., Ferretti, D., & Michelini, E. (2014). Role of multiaxial state of stress on cracking of RC ties. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 123, 21–33.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2014.02.011>
- C. Mias, L. Torres, M. Guadagnini, A. Turon. (2015). *Short and long-term cracking behavior of GFRP reinforced concrete beams*.
- Carvelli, V., Pisani, M. A., & Poggi, C. (2010). Fatigue behaviour of concrete bridge deck slabs reinforced with GFRP bars. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 41(7), 560–567.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2010.06.006>
- CNR. (2007). *Guide for the design and construction of concrete structures reinforced with fiber-reinforced polymer bars* (CNR-DT 203/2006). Italian Research Council Rome.
- CSA. (2009). *Design and construction of building components with fibre-reinforced polymers* (CAN/CSA-S806-02).
- Ehsani, M. R., Saadatmanesh, H., & Tao, S. (1997). Bond Behavior of Deformed GFRP Rebars. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 31(14), 1413–1430.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/002199839703101404>
- El-Nemr, A., Ahmed, E. A., Barris, C., & Benmokrane, B. (2016). Bond-dependent coefficient of glass- and carbon-FRP bars in normal- and high-strength concretes. *Construction and Building Materials*, 113, 77–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.03.005>
- Fib. (2001). *fib Bulletins 14. Externally bonded FRP reinforcement for RC structures*. fib. The International Federation for Structural Concrete. <https://www.fib-international.org/publications/fib-bulletins/externally-bonded-frp-reinforcement-for-rc-structures-detail.html>
- Focacci, F., & Carloni, C. (2015). Periodic variation of the transferable load at the FRP-masonry interface. *Composite Structures*, 129, 90–100.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.03.008>
- Lee, J.-Y., Kim, T.-Y., Kim, T.-J., Yi, C.-K., Park, J.-S., You, Y.-C., & Park, Y.-H. (2008). Interfacial bond strength of glass fiber reinforced polymer bars in high-strength concrete. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 39(2), 258–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2007.03.008>
- Mazaheripour, H., Barros, J. A. O., Sena-Cruz, J. M., Pepe, M., & Martinelli, E. (2013). Experimental study on bond performance of GFRP bars in self-compacting steel fiber reinforced concrete. *Composite Structures*, 95, 202–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.07.009>
- Mufti, A. A., & Neale, K. W. (2008). *State-of-the-Art of FRP and SHM Applications in Bridge Structures in Canada*. 2(2), 10.
- Pendhari, S. S., Kant, T., & Desai, Y. M. (2008). Application of polymer composites in civil construction: A general review. *Composite Structures*, 84(2), 114–124.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2007.06.007>
- Sireg Geotech S r. l. (2017). *Glasspreetech Technical Data Sheet (provided privately by the manufacturer)*. Provided privately by the manufacturer. Provided privately by the manufacturer
- Zhao, X., Minhajur Rahman, M., D'Antino, T., Focacci, F., & Carloni, C. (2022). Effect of bonded length on the load response and failure mode of pull-out tests of GFRP bars embedded in concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 347, 128425.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.128425>